

Bridging the IUCN Global Standard with governance and engagement tools: multi-method lessons from five Mediterranean case studies for strengthening water security

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ABSTRACT

In the Mediterranean region, water security is increasingly threatened as climate-induced scarcity and burgeoning agricultural demand create a structural imbalance that exceeds the regenerative capacity of natural hydrological systems. While local Nature-based Solutions (NbS) offer a pathway to resilience through diverse socio-environmental co-benefits, their widespread uptake remains hindered by a recognized deficit in standardized methodologies and comprehensive performance valuation. The aim of this study is to identify key lessons from the assessment of five Full Water-Cycle Nature-based Solutions (FWC-NbS) case studies (CS) within agricultural settings, utilizing the International Union for Conservation of Nature Global Standard for NbS (IUCN GS). While the IUCN GS demonstrably identifies challenges and opportunities for improving NbS design and implementation, its application can impose a top-down structure, potentially limiting its ability to fully capture the complexity of small-scale interventions. To mitigate this, a multi-method approach incorporating governance and engagement tools, particularly co-design processes facilitated by a Mediterranean Community of Practice (MedCoP), provides a critical complementary bottom-up perspective. The results support that the IUCN Global Standard is a robust, systematic framework that substantially strengthens NbS design and facilitates the

Abbreviations: CS, Case Study; FIA, Forested Infiltration Area; IUCN GS, IUCN Global Standard; FWC-NbS, Full-Water Cycle Nature-based Solutions; MAR, Managed Aquifer Recharge; MedCoP, Mediterranean Community of Practice; PRIMA, Partnership for Research and Innovation in the Mediterranean Area.

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identification of opportunities and recommendations. Moreover, the integrated multi-methodology establishes a potent system that reinforces operational protocols within site-specific contexts. This combined approach corroborates the IUCN GS challenge identification, promotes participatory governance, effectively integrates local knowledge, and captures crucial site-specific nuances. The combined application of the IUCN GS and the multi-method approach has yielded site-specific recommendations for enhancing water security across the five FWC-NbS interventions. However, the operationalization of these NbS, despite their inherent potential, presents critical implementation challenges, particularly constraints related to data scarcity driven by budget and time limitations.

1. Introduction

The Mediterranean region is a global hotspot subject to escalating water scarcity and pressure [1–3]. Over the past decades, the inherent hydroclimatic characteristics of the region, marked by arid and semi-arid conditions with protracted dry summers and naturally constrained water availability [4], have been under increasing strain due to the elevated water demands associated with irrigation-intensive agricultural practices, representing now between 70% and 80% of total water use in Southern Europe [5], frequently surpassing ecologically and hydrologically sustainable thresholds. The detrimental effects of farming practices on water quality include salinization and pollution [6]. Agriculture and farming practices not only contribute to water-related issues but are also deeply impacted by the very challenges they create [7]. Climate change is expected to exacerbate pre-existing vulnerabilities, particularly in areas where water scarcity is already a significant concern [8,9]. Existing and future anthropogenic stressors compromise water reservoirs [10], threaten the integrity of fluvial ecosystems in Mediterranean regions [11] and could exacerbate social unrest, ranging from local community clashes to international tensions and inequalities in water access [12].

To improve water management in Mediterranean basins, integrated water approaches for good governance and Nature-based Solutions (NbS) are needed [13,14]. In fact, NbS with safeguards to ensure they do not have negative side effects on biodiversity or ecosystem functions, are estimated to provide up to 37% of climate change mitigation needs to limit global warming to below 2 °C until 2030 [15]. Local NbS have been recognized to generate multiple co-benefits, allowing communities to adapt to specific climate impacts and provide long term resilience. Conversely, these interventions are at risk of failure due to poor governance or simplified biodiversity [16]. A systemic perspective is essential for the effective implementation of NbS. Such an approach necessitates a comprehensive understanding of the interconnected natural and socio-cultural dynamics inherent to a given context, requiring solutions that arise from the co-design process and respond to societal needs [17]. NbS should be informed by socio-ecological systems and guided by the willingness to revise project goals, values, and expectations during their design and implementation [18]. Moreover, socio-cultural dynamics are essential for sufficient water management, as they fundamentally shape how communities interact with and value water [19]. These dynamics involve community relations, dictating cooperation or conflict over resources [20]; cultural perceptions, influencing conservation and policy acceptance [21]; and decision-making structures, which often blend formal and traditional approaches. Understanding these multifaceted factors is crucial for effective and sustainable water management [22], which aims to ensure that water resources meet current human, economic and environmental needs, without compromising the ability of future generations to meet theirs. To achieve these goals, it is necessary to consider the entire hydrological cycle and shift toward circular and holistic approaches, ensuring that key ecological functions and ecosystem services are maintained over time [23]. NbS may be cost-effective in addressing water management issues in agriculture, improving water quantity and quality while improving ecosystem functions, and addressing conservation, climatic and socioeconomic challenges [24,25]. However, the knowledge needed

for widespread implementation is insufficient [26]. Likewise, NbS for water management face challenges related to fragmented governance, integrated operation, regulatory barriers, diverse stakeholders' values and perceptions, insufficient understanding of costs and benefits, poor stakeholders' engagement, inefficient communication strategies [27] and lack of standardized methodologies to evaluate their performance and upscale solutions [28]. In certain instances, the synergistic operation of NbS and grey infrastructure can reduce performance uncertainty, strengthen water management practices, improve infrastructure efficiency and sustainability [29] and unlock private capital for environmental conservation [30].

The International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) published the IUCN Global Standard for Nature-based Solutions (IUCN GS) in July 2020 to provide clarity and precision to the NbS concept, aiming for a shared understanding, overcoming some challenges related to design and implementation and long-term sustainability of the solutions. The IUCN GS is an overarching framework for the design, verification, and scaling up of NbS [31,32], which substantially supports the implementation and mainstreaming of NbS [33]. Supported by the IUCN with periodic updates, the IUCN GS is acknowledged in recent studies as a state-of-the-art tool for its systematic guidance on terrestrial [34], marine [35], and fluvial [36] ecosystems. While case studies applying the Standard exist, research on its widespread application in different ecosystems, biomes and socioeconomic contexts as a comprehensive assessment framework is lacking [31,37] and there is a need for more evaluations of NbS performance, to prove their effectiveness, demonstrate their value, and improve and scale up future projects [33]. The increased application of the IUCN GS could enable uniform assessment, facilitate systematic comparisons, and lead to a database for refining existing NbS and designing new ones [32]. Applying the IUCN GS can significantly contribute to overcoming societal challenges, offering a robust framework that enhances the effectiveness and sustainability of solutions, provides strong guidance for upscaling, and facilitates stakeholder engagement and adaptive management, particularly for water management projects [38,36,39]. Some authors highlight that the IUCN GS contributes to sustainable water resource management in the Mediterranean and offers a valuable holistic tool for evaluating the processes of NbS that complements other existing frameworks, as it is designed to be applied to all project phases, societal challenges, and environmental contexts [40,38]. It has long been recognized that the engagement of appropriate stakeholders, effective communication, and good governance are key to overcoming NbS implementation barriers, such as institutional resistance, superficial participation, and sustainability challenges [41]. Participatory evaluation and co-design approaches can contribute to a better NbS design and implementation, establish goals, and support communities by identifying their needs [42]. The IUCN GS acknowledges this and offers assistance by providing guidance on the identification of the expertise, concerns and needs of key stakeholders [31].

In this study, the IUCN GS has been applied alongside combined governance and engagement tools to the five case studies (CS) within the NATMed project. NATMed is an EU-funded project through the PRIMA Programme (Partnership for Research and Innovation in the Mediterranean Area), which focuses on NbS for resilient water management in the Mediterranean, acknowledging the fact that the water supply

becomes inadequate to meet the increasing demand, particularly in the agricultural sector and within the context of climate change. NATMed aims to develop, apply, and validate a set of five Full Water Cycle - NbS (FWC-NbS). FWC-NbS refers to the expected increased impact of the designed NbS on the entire hydrological process, as they have been integrated into existing grey and natural water infrastructures. They are aimed at optimizing water-related and water-dependent ecosystem services, becoming an essential step thanks to the provision of multiple co-benefits. In particular, the FWC-NbS implemented are expected to benefit several water-cycle phases (capture, storage, treatment, distribution and irrigation).

This paper provides an analysis of the main areas for improvement on NbS design and performance across societal challenges, design, biodiversity net-gain, economic feasibility, inclusive governance, trade-off balancing, adaptive management, and sustainability and mainstreaming in five NbS for water security [43,27,16] in an agricultural context, all guided by the IUCN GS for NbS. The five CS are used as a test-bed for applying a combined set of governance and engagement tools (co-design process and MedCoP) supporting the IUCN GS assessment under a similar context of water-related problems. Opportunities, challenges and lessons learned to enhance NbS design and facilitate implementation are being discussed.

A Mediterranean Community of Practice (MedCoP) has been established to reinforce operational protocols and better understand the barriers to the implementation of NbS within site-specific contexts. Communities of Practice (CoP), described as groups of people who share a concern or a passion for something they do and learn how to do it better as they interact regularly [44], are particularly suitable for complex, place-based sustainability challenges such as water management in the Mediterranean [45]. MedCoP embodies these dimensions by bringing together diverse stakeholders around the shared goal of improving water security through FWC-NbS, fostering sustained collaboration, co-learning and recognizing that equitable engagement strengthens both the design and acceptance of NbS.

The present study aims to address the following research questions:

- i) What key lessons, opportunities and challenges are revealed by applying the IUCN Standard to these five case studies?
- ii) What are the potential benefits derived from combining the use of the IUCN Standard with community-based governance processes (co-design process and MedCoP) in these five case studies?

2. Methodology

2.1. Five case study areas

The five CS all feature solutions that address local water management challenges such as water imbalance, scarcity, inefficient water infrastructure, water pollution and lack of integrated solutions. These solutions are framed within an agricultural context, and generally combine different NbS and grey solutions to maximize performance. The CS are a representation of diverse socio-economic and bioclimatic zones; this diversity is scientifically necessary to validate whether the proposed multi-method framework—combining the IUCN GS with bottom-up governance—is robust and flexible enough to capture local nuances while maintaining standardized quality. Here is a brief description of each of them; for more information, see [40].

CS1: *carrión de los céspedes*, Spain (Area: 4.1 ha.)

The pilot in Seville serves as an experimental living lab for the co-creation, experimentation, and evaluation of innovative water products, wastewater treatment solutions, and circular economy approaches. It focuses on co-creating and testing new water solutions. In this case study, constructed wetlands, floating gardens, and ultrasound methods for wastewater treatment and water storage have been tested. The goal is to produce reclaimed water for crop irrigation in agricultural lands,

offering a sustainable alternative to conventional methods.

CS2: *Chimaditida lake system*, Greece (Area: 960 ha.)

Located in Western Macedonia, Lake Chimaditida is part of the Natura 2000 Network. This case study aims to enhance water quality and natural wetland storage. This is achieved through the implementation of rotational livestock grazing (Greek buffaloes) by fencing selected areas, which controls reed population and conserves the lake. Additionally, riparian buffers along the shore will allow for the mitigation of environmental pollution, such as pesticide run-off from agricultural activities, therefore improving water quality. Furthermore, the existence of natural wastewater treatment systems made it possible to explore the use of wastewater for agricultural irrigation, reducing water consumption and fertilization.

CS3: *Arborea region*, Italy (Area: 0.5 ha.)

In the Arborea region of Sardinia, designated as a Nitrate Vulnerable Zone due to intensive agricultural and farming practices, a Managed Aquifer Recharge (MAR) system based on the Forested Infiltration Area (FIA) technique [46] has been upgraded. This system channels drainage water through a network of trenches and wooded patches to recharge the aquifer while reducing nitrate groundwater contamination. A comprehensive monitoring network is also in place to assess its effectiveness.

CS4: *Bozcaada Island*, Türkiye (Area: 37.6 ha.)

On Bozcaada Island, the NbS deployed for sustainable water management and climate change adaptation include MAR systems, such as infiltration ponds and reinjection wells. In addition, soil management and climate-resilient agriculture practices, through treated wastewater reuse for crop irrigation, have been implemented. Equally, the project also incorporates Water 4.0 technologies by improving the water distribution system and creating a network of monitoring wells.

CS5: *Oued Righ Canal*, Algeria (Area: 1.2 ha.)

In Algeria's Righ Valley, this case study focuses on treating and purifying domestic wastewater before discharging it in the Oued Righ canal. A pilot-scale system of various constructed wetlands (French system) has been implemented, providing reused water for agricultural irrigation. This innovative prototype is designed for wastewater treatment and strategically aligns with the Touggourt wastewater treatment plant and the Oued Righ canal. Furthermore, the project also focused on restoring the banks of a specific section of the Oued Righ Canal. This canal bank restoration, along with existing gray infrastructure, will help reduce erosion, improve water quality, and support local biodiversity. This approach seeks to enhance the ecological functions and benefits provided by the canal, contributing to the overall environmental sustainability of the waterway.

2.2. The IUCN global standard for NbS

To ensure that NbS are designed effectively and efficiently, the IUCN Global Standard (GS) has been applied to NATMed's five CS. The IUCN GS provides a holistic framework to assist with design, evaluate impact, assess progress, and refine the implementation of NbS. The core of the IUCN GS consists of eight criteria, which are defined as the essential principles that a project's design must adhere to be recognized by the IUCN as an NbS. The IUCN also identifies seven significant societal challenges NbS can address [43]. Each of the eight criteria is composed of three to five indicators, serving as design principles or qualitative evaluation parameters. A detailed description of each indicator is provided in Supplementary Table 1. The IUCN offers concise guidance on these criteria and indicators, supplemented by in-depth information and a self-assessment tool. This tool enables users to semi-quantitatively assess a project's adherence to the indicators, ultimately calculating the percentage match to each criterion and determining overall

adherence to the Standard. The overall adherence rating obtained is based on a traffic light system per indicator, going from “Strong adherence” (dark green) to “Insufficient” (red) (see legend within Supplementary Table 2). For more information, IUCN has a Guidance for using the IUCN GS [47].

In this study, an assessment against the IUCN GS was conducted twice for NATMed’s five CS using the existing IUCN self-assessment tool. For this purpose, each case study assigned a technical team to self-assess its own FWC-NbS: once at the beginning of the project (from July 2023 to February 2024), coinciding with the co-design phase, and again during the implementation and monitoring phase (from April 2025 to July 2025), as shown in Fig. 4. The initial assessment identified several challenges and opportunities that have the potential for replication and upscaling, along with a series of lessons learnt for enhancing the obtained score, as it was the first contact of CS with the framework. These recommendations aimed to improve the NbS in a wide range of fields related to each of the IUCN GS criteria, including design, performance, biodiversity outcomes, public acceptance, governance, economic sustainability, monitoring, communication, policy alignment and impact. When possible, the recommendations were incorporated into the NbS development of the CS. The goal of the second assessment was to distil all the developed good practices and proven useful recommendations, refining previous information and adapting it according to project updates and CS development, following implementation and monitoring outputs. The process was guided, supervised and reviewed by one of the NATMed project partners, holding the professional certificate on the IUCN Global Standard for NbS, awarded by the IUCN Academy. Both assessments were self-conducted by each of the CS, and the same methodology was followed, which has been previously described in [40]. The challenges identified were divided into site-specific (e.g. those climate-related) and those common to all CS.

Technicians from each CS participated in an internal survey that was conducted following the initial round of the assessment via Google Forms, to ascertain the areas in which CS required additional insights from the support team, thereby enhance the assessment process (internal survey available as dataset, data availability section).

2.3. Co-design framework

2.3.1. Stakeholders mapping

In line with the foundational work of Ferreira *et al.* (2023) [42], which identifies stakeholder mapping as a critical precursor for an effective engagement strategy, this study implemented a systematic mapping approach. This process was designed to ensure the active involvement of all pertinent actors throughout the entire project lifecycle, from initial design through implementation. The primary objective of the stakeholder mapping was two-fold: first, to systematically identify and categorize all relevant groups, ranging from institutions to individuals, within the water management sector; and second, to clarify their respective perceptions, roles, influence, and interests.

Furthermore, the mapping contributed to a structured understanding of the complex socio-institutional landscape specific to each case study area. The resulting socio-political data from semi-structured interviews directly supported the creation of the Mediterranean Community of Practice (MedCoP) and provided critical, context-specific input for the iterative co-design sessions conducted during workshop sessions. The stakeholder mapping process was developed and executed across six distinct phases (as illustrated in Fig. 1), which included: the formation of the mapping team and scope definition; comprehensive stakeholder identification; the execution of semi-structured interviews; and the formulation of evidence-based recommendations to enhance engagement and governance within the MedCoP.

2.3.2. Mediterranean community of practice (MedCoP) in the NATMed case studies

The MedCoP was established to facilitate the integration of knowledge, experiences, and practices across five diverse Mediterranean case studies within NATMed. Its overarching goal is to support the co-design, implementation, evaluation, and eventual replication of FWC-NbS, addressing site-specific water management challenges while offering a scalable model for broader Mediterranean application.

For the purpose of this study, stakeholder mapping and the MedCoP represent complementary but distinct components of the engagement framework. Stakeholder mapping served as a diagnostic and planning tool, while the MedCoP functioned as the operational participatory platform where identified actors engaged in dialogue, co-design, and co-evaluation activities. Crucially, the stakeholder mapping process generated the necessary socio-political data—specifically actor typologies, power asymmetries, and potential conflicting interests—which was then operationalized by the MedCoP. This systematic approach ensured balanced representation and appropriate engagement levels within MedCoP, preventing arbitrary assembly. The different levels of stakeholder engagement, which characterize the intensity of involvement and breadth of reach, were defined during the preceding stakeholder mapping process (Fig. 2). MedCoP interactions subsequently generated additional insights that refined the initial stakeholder analysis and supported adaptive governance.

As illustrated in Fig. 4, the MedCoP is integrated within the design and implementation of the FWC-NbS. It functions as a multi-actor ecosystem designed to transition planning from a top-down model to one grounded in relevant local context, thereby promoting inclusive and collaborative environments. This is achieved through primary mechanisms, including iterative co-design workshops (Fig. 4), socio-political knowledge integration (Fig. 1), stakeholder’s multi-level participation (Fig. 2), and continuous feedback loops (Fig. 3). These feedback loops allow participants to raise concerns or propose design and implementation adjustments, which are reviewed and discussed during MedCoP meetings to maintain a participatory and responsive process (Fig. 3).

Fig. 1. Phases that supported stakeholders mapping in each case of study. Phase 1: assembling the mapping team, purpose and scope definition; Phase 2: identification of main stakeholders, aiming to collect information on the needs and perceptions of the participants; Phase 3: gathering comprehensive data related to social variables, as case studies’ diagnosis, risks and outcomes of each MedCoP session; Phase 4: semi-structured interviews; Phase 5: definition and analysis of local perceptions, needs and cognitive barriers of beneficiaries; and Phase 6: recommendations for engagement and governance based on priority and feasibility.

Fig. 2. The three levels of engagement, with arrows flowing from Level 1 to Level 3, indicate decreasing intensity of involvement but increasing breadth of reach.

Fig. 3. The feedback mechanism within MedCoP ensures continuous participation and a responsive process.

2.3.3. Methodology for co-design within MedCoP

The MedCoP directly supported the co-design framework by facilitating iterative learning, adaptive management, and cross-case collaboration. By functioning within the MedCoP, the co-design sessions could draw on shared experiences and resources from other CS. Three workshops were organized with co-design sessions developed in each case study area, as presented in Fig. 4.

In this study, only co-design results that were used to assist NbS

design and implementation and that allowed for ongoing comparison against the IUCN GS, were considered (see Table 4). The co-design methodology comprised three sessions, each associated with a specific objective and methodological approach. Particularly, the three co-design sessions followed a detailed structure common to all the CS and addressed issues related to the IUCN GS criteria, see Table 4. The first and second co-design sessions were conducted before implementation, and the third session was conducted after implementation.

Fig. 4. Flowchart showing the different steps during the design and implementation of the FWC-NbS. This figure illustrates the interlinkage of various governance and engagement tools (stakeholder mapping, MedCoP, and NbS co-design) that support the assessment against the IUCN Global Standard. These tools are connected through a feedback and reinforcement loop and all together feed into the final assessment of the five case studies and inform the development of guidelines for the NATMed project.

Each one of the sessions was developed in the local language and guided by the project's on-site partners. The minutes after the sessions were made available to project partners. The first co-design session served to introduce the project's objectives and vision, identifying the societal challenges present in the area. The second session deepened the co-design process by aligning the vision of the FWC-NbS with local needs and aspirations, refining the design. It also focused on identifying strengths, weaknesses, and obstacles for FWC-NbS implementation, as well as possible trade-offs. During the three sessions, several engagement and co-creation tools were used: strengths-based strategic analysis (SOAR) (Stavros & Hinrichs, 2009) [48], including strategic visioning and pathway planning (5 Bold Steps vision canvas [49]), and visual prototyping techniques (*storyboarding*) to explore technical and legislative aspects of NbS (UNaLab, Tools for Co-creation, n.d.) [50]. The third co-design session was primarily focused on assessing the NbS implemented for their adaptive management potential and incorporating stakeholder feedback on their implementation. To help stakeholders provide specific feedback and strengthen ownership, several co-design tools were applied, including reflective peer-review to critically validate ideas (*Critical Friend*) [51], structured ideation and improvement prompts (*I Like, I Wish, What If* [52]), and early-stage evaluation to assess feasibility and refine implementation choices (*Pilot Appraisal* [53]). More information on the specific techniques applied can be consulted at UNaLab, Tools for Co-creation (n.d.) [50]. The overall structure of the three workshops, including co-design session periods, output description and relation to the IUCN GS, has been described in Section 3.2.2. (Table 4). The link with IUCN GS criteria was established using the engagement and co-creation tools previously explained. For instance, the first co-design session focused on identifying societal challenges using 5 bold steps vision canvas, which was related to criterion 1 and the pathway planning or roadmap that aligns with criterion 3 of the IUCN GS.

2.4. The IUCN GS for nbs, governance and engagement

The connectivity between the stakeholder mapping, the MedCoP, co-design and the IUCN Global Standard functions as a synergistic ecosystem connected by a continuous flow of information (see Fig. 4). The governance and engagement tools, from the stakeholder mapping to

the MedCoP and co-design sessions, are linked by a bottom-up data flow. For instance, outputs from stakeholder mapping and MedCoP sessions—specifically social data and local perceptions such as stakeholder opinions, local context or challenges—directly provide the initial materials informing the IUCN GS assessment, ensuring compliance is grounded in empirical local context. Conducting stakeholders mapping prior to the creation of MedCoP and the application of the GS serve as the foundational link that connects the social context to the technical framework, ensuring that the community's composition of MedCoP is representative. The co-design sessions served as a supportive tool for reinforcing the IUCN GS self-assessment and the flow of information from the co-design sessions was integrated into its different criteria. The co-design process ensures that stakeholder engagement is targeted specifically to improve the project's adherence to the GS. There is also an operational symmetry, since the frameworks interlock to facilitate Adaptive Management (IUCN GS Criterion 7). The MedCoP acts as a vehicle for adaptive management, providing the structured feedback mechanism to evolve NbS design and implementation.

3. Results

3.1. IUCN global standard self-assessment alignment

The first assessment allowed the identification of a series of challenges, which were ratified and/or completed in the second assessment. In the following Table 1 a summary of the key issues per criterion can be found, distinguishing between those that apply to all case studies and those that apply only to specific ones. For the complete version see Supplementary Table 3.

The full set of results from the two assessments against the IUCN GS can be found in the associated datasets (data availability section). Challenges first encountered in conjunction with the proposed recommendations resulted in altered practices in some instances, leading to an enhanced level of adherence to the Standard in the CS. Here, a comparison between the percentage of alignment to the Standard for each criterion (criterion 1 - Societal Challenges, criterion 2 - Design at scale, criterion 3 - Biodiversity net-gain, criterion 4 - Economic feasibility, criterion 5 - Inclusive Governance, criterion 6 - Balance trade-offs, criterion 7 - Adaptive Management, criterion 8 - Sustainability and

Table 1

Summary of the main challenges identified through the process of assessment against the IUCN GS for the five case studies. Challenges are categorized by criterion and separated by those common to all case studies and those site-specific.

	Common Challenges (All Case Studies)	Site-Specific Challenges
Criterion 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Water scarcity and security - Environmental degradation and pollution - Low public awareness and participation - Need for effective stakeholder-led processes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CS2: Transition from lignite-based energy and mining legacy - CS3: Compliance with Nitrate Vulnerable Zone (NVZ) mandates - CS4: Balancing tourism versus agriculture water demands - CS5: High groundwater temperatures
Criterion 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Complex regulatory hurdles and authorizations - Identifying and managing cross-sector risks - Scaling up solutions to wider territories - Ensuring long-term stakeholder participation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CS2: Natura 2000 Network specific environmental authorizations - CS3: Managing nitrate pollution at a regional dimension - CS5: Preventing illegal waste dumping in canals
Criterion 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of baseline data and clear metrics/KPIs - Limited time, funding, and technical expertise - Managing biodiversity and ecosystem integrity - Challenges in ecological connectivity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CS2: Balancing bird conservation (SPA status) with reed bed reduction - CS4: Managing intense soil erosion and drought - CS5: Managing shallow water tables to prevent aquifer pollution
Criterion 4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High upfront costs and lack of funding mechanisms - Difficulty quantifying "intangible" ecosystem benefits - Lack of structured business models for post-project maintenance - Limited financial data and expertise 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CS2: Regional lack of entrepreneurship culture - CS3: Determining economic feasibility - CS4: Failure to monetize labour and fertility gains in technical data - CS5: Detailed life-cycle cost comparisons versus traditional engineering
Criterion 5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Overcoming barriers to inclusion for vulnerable groups - Need for formal grievance resolution mechanisms - Balancing divergent stakeholder interests and power imbalances - Documenting informal meetings/processes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CS1: Low local digital access and technical language issues - CS3: Engagement with local people and diverse farmer backgrounds - CS4: Seasonal fluctuations in stakeholder availability
Criterion 6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Establishing robust KPIs and Risk Management Plans - Mapping spatial and temporal trade-offs - Defining long-term stakeholder rights and roles - Funding constraints for corrective measures 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CS2: Environmental damage from soil compaction - CS3: Technical inability of Passive Treatment Systems to reduce phosphate - CS4: Conflict between tourism and agriculture sectors
Criterion 7	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Securing funding to sustain monitoring post-project - Periodically revising monitoring and evaluation plans - Institutionalizing iterative learning and adaptation cycles - Gap between short project timelines and long-term responses 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CS1: Handling seasonal variations in monitoring - CS2: Aligning plans with previous river basin management parameters
Criterion 8	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Regulatory and institutional barriers - Lack of policy incentives and standards for NbS - Knowledge transfer and communication gaps - Influencing political decision-making and legislation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CS2: Integrating conservation into Post-Lignite/Just Transition frameworks - CS4: Delays caused by changes in local administration - CS5: Limited knowledge of constructed wetlands among regulators

Mainstreaming) has been made for the first and the second assessment. Results per case study are presented in Fig. 5.

The second assessment generally demonstrated a higher or maintained level of alignment to the IUCN GS across all criteria and CS. The overall adherence to the IUCN GS for each case study after the second assessment resulted in 78.4% for CS1, 68.1% for CS2, 81.5% for CS3, 72.5% for CS4 and 60.9% for CS5 (see Supplementary Table 2). The second-stage evaluation enabled CS to iteratively refine interventions by integrating baseline recommendations such as methodological improvements into the design, notably in addressing previously identified challenges. In CS3, the technical team operationalized recommendations to determine economic feasibility by conducting a cost-benefit analysis for the FIA pilot. This enhanced its adherence to Criterion 4, specifically by providing data for Indicators 4.1 and 4.2 and conducting a comparative inventory of alternative solutions for Indicator 4.3. Similarly, CS1 utilized the findings to refine its participatory model under Criterion 5, acknowledging existing deficits in the engagement of underrepresented groups.

A slight decrease in adherence to the IUCN GS was observed for certain criteria/indicators. For instance, in CS2 and Criterion 4: economic feasibility decreased from 83% during the first assessment to 58% in the second (Fig. 5-b), as the expected level of economic assessment, including non-monetary and delayed benefits analysis, was found to be incomplete. Similarly, CS1, CS4 and CS5 registered a score decrease for some indicators, without affecting the final corresponding criterion score (see Table 2).

Table 2 shows the total increase (positive) or decrease (negative) in the adherence percentage for each criterion, in accordance with the IUCN GS indicators, across the five CS. Data has been shown as numerical percentage variation in the corresponding column. The color scale indicates the number of points higher or lower per criterion, as a result obtained from comparing score changes from the first to the second assessment for all indicators. The type of change per indicator, as detailed in the legend, has been shown as (=) no changes, one or several (+) indicating one or more score points higher, whereas one or multiple (-) indicating one or more score points lower. According to the results of the second assessment the ranking of criteria that shows a higher positive percentage of change is Cr4>Cr2>Cr7>Cr3>Cr5>Cr8>Cr1>Cr6. Criterion 4 reached the highest increase (75) in CS3. Criterion 2 showed positive changes for at least one indicator in all CS. Criterion 3 demonstrated an increment of one point for all indicators in CS3, analogous to the pattern observed in Criterion 8 in CS5. On the other hand, some CS reported a decrease in the score for some indicators, such as indicator 8.3 in CS1, indicator 4.1 and 4.2 in CS2, indicator 4.2 in CS4, or indicators 2.3, 5.1 and 5.2, and 6.2 in CS5.

The variations in adherence scores presented in Table 2 reflect the transition from a theoretical design phase to an active implementation and monitoring stage, and it reflects the iterative learning process facilitated by the application of the IUCN GS. The IUCN definition of the Standard states that, regardless of its overall match score, a NbS cannot be considered as adhering to the Standard if any one of its eight criteria is rated "insufficient" [47]. Based on this definition, all case studies align with the Standard, as confirmed by the results of the second assessment. All indicators rated as insufficient during the first assessment, were rated above insufficient in the second one (See Supplementary Table 2). The application of the Standard twice demonstrated to contribute to the enhancement of interventions across a diverse range of domains which was reflected as positive shifts, particularly for criteria 4 and 2. Furthermore, positive shifts indicate that the technical teams successfully integrated early recommendations, such as performing comparative inventories of alternative solutions and detailed cost-benefit analyses. CS's were more aware of certain aspects that were not originally given significant consideration. Conversely, the decreased scores (e.g., indicator 4.1 in CS2 or 6.2 in CS5) should be interpreted as a refinement of the self-assessment accuracy. Negative shifts have also highlighted difficulties in addressing all of the Standard requirements or

Fig. 5. Criteria (C1 to C8) scores and overall match showing the percentage of adherence to the IUCN GS for the first and the second assessment in each case study. a) CS1 - Spain, b) CS2 - Greece, c) CS3- Italy, d) CS4 - Türkiye and e) CS5 - Algeria.

guidelines, due many times to budget and time limitations that led to data scarcity, as it exceeded the technical scope of the project, as found

in the internal survey.

Results from the internal survey, which comprised a total of seven

Fig. 5. (continued).

answers (see results in dataset), also showed that Criterion 1 was qualified as "easy" or "somewhat easy" by four participants, thus being selected as the easiest. Conversely, Criterion 4 and 6 were each awarded five and four votes for "hard" and "somewhat hard", respectively, and were thus identified as the most difficult ones. This aligns with the generally low initial scores in criterion 4, supporting the idea that the second round of assessment improved the holistic perception of NbS provided by the Standard. In addition, despite the inherent differences in participants' perceptions, it is pertinent to note that none of the criteria were rated as "easy" or "somewhat easy" on average, and that there were merely two votes for "easy" across the entire survey, in contrast to six votes for "hard".

3.2. MedCoP and co-design process outcomes

3.2.1. Results from the stakeholders mapping

A total of 15 semi-structured interviews were conducted—three per

case study—targeting the following stakeholder profiles: (1) technical and academic experts, (2) public authority representatives, and (3) community or final user representatives. Stakeholders were categorized by type and role, and their levels of interest and influence were analyzed to support strategic engagement planning. Qualitative data analysis of semi-structured interviews categorizing results of all case studies are shown in Supplementary Table 4. Information from the interviews contributed to understanding the necessities of the stakeholders for each case of study. A selection of these data served as materials for organizing the co-design workshops and MedCoP meetings.

3.2.2. Results from the co-design process

Data collected through co-design workshops (stakeholder feedback across the five case studies) were systematically reviewed to identify recurring themes, shared challenges, and emerging opportunities. Session reports, interview notes, and workshop documentation were analyzed to detect cross-cutting patterns observed across multiple

Table 2

Total increased (percentage variation > 0) or decreased (percentage variation < 0), including legend, during the second assessment compared to results from the first assessment for all indicators across the five case studies.

IUCN Global Standard		CS1 (Spain)		CS2 (Greece)		CS3 (Italy)		CS4 (Türkiye)		CS5 (Algeria)	
Criteria	Indicators	Changes	Total variation in %	Changes	Total variation in %	Changes	Total variation in %	Changes	Total variation in %	Changes	Total variation in %
1 Societal Challenges	1.1	=	11	=	0	=	22	=	22	=	0
	1.2	=		=		=		=			
	1.3	+		=		++		++			
2 Design at scale	2.1	+	23	=	11	+	34	+	11	=	0
	2.2	+		=		=		=			
	2.3	=		+		++		=		-	
3 Biodiversity net-gain	3.1	=	8	=	16	+	33	=	0	=	8
	3.2	=		=		+		=			
	3.3	=		+		+		=		+	
	3.4	+		+		+		=		=	
4 Economic feasibility	4.1	=	25	-	-25	++	75	=	0	+	25
	4.2	+		--		++		-		=	
	4.3	+		=		++		+		+	
	4.4	+		=		+++		=		+	
5 Inclusive governance	5.1	+	20	=	20	=	20	=	0	-	0
	5.2	+		=		=		=		-	
	5.3	=		=		+		=		=	
	5.4	+		+		++		=		+	
	5.5	=		++		=		+			
6 Balance trade-offs	6.1	=	11	=	0	+	11	=	11	+	0
	6.2	=		=		=		=		-	
	6.3	+		=		=		+		=	
7 Adaptive management	7.1	=	11	=	11	+	22	=	22	=	0
	7.2	+		=		=		+		=	
	7.3	=		+		+		=			
8 Sustainability/Mainstreaming	8.1	+	0	=	0	+	22	=	0	+	34
	8.2	=		=		+		+			
	8.3	-		=		=		-		+	

< - -	Two or more score points lower
-	One score point lower
=	No changes
+	One score point higher
++	Two score points higher
+++	Three score points higher
++++	Four score points higher
> +++++	More than four score points higher

contexts rather than isolated case-specific findings. The main synthesis of recurring themes and insights emerging across MedCoP discussion are summarized in Table 3 which presents different categories and main takeaways. Although the co-design process is still ongoing, with the third round of workshops currently underway in some cases studies (CS3, CS4 and CS5), this work highlights several common findings across all sessions. The decision to present these results at this stage was guided by the NATMed project’s methodological framework and the project’s dissemination timeline for academic reporting. It has been acknowledged that the timeline of EU-funded projects’ research and dissemination activities often runs in parallel with implementation phases.

Table 4 presents the structure of the co-design sessions and the relation found with the IUCN Standard’s criteria. The indicators that each session has helped to complete are indicated in the column IUCN

GS relation. All of the three sessions applied methodologies that promote equitable participation (Indicator 5.2 of the IUCN GS), ensuring the inclusion of diverse stakeholder groups (Indicator 5.3), documenting the decision-making process and sharing the outcomes of the co-design process (Indicator 5.4), which aligns with criterion 5.

The first session served to introduce the project’s objectives and vision, identifying the societal challenges in each case of study (Indicator 1.2), ensuring that the NbS to be designed addressed those specific challenges (Indicator 1.1), which aligns with criterion 1. Equally, NbS design should adequately manage challenges related to biodiversity and local ecosystems (Indicator 3.1), aligning with criterion 3. Participants validated the designated intervention area, aligning with criterion 2. In addition, this session allowed for diverse feedback collection from local stakeholders on the NbS (Indicators 5.3, 5.4). The second session deepened the co-design process by aligning the vision of the NbS with

Table 3

Takeaways from the co-design process and MedCoP.

Category	Takeaways from co-design and MedCoP
Early & Continuous Stakeholder Involvement Barriers to Engagement	It is crucial for shaping interventions, building trust, and ensuring adoption/ownership of NbS. Local authorities lack NbS experience/skilled personnel; capacity building is essential.
Motivating Participation	Challenges due to competing priorities and skepticism. Effective NbS communication requires clearly demonstrating its benefits and thoughtful facilitation.
Bridging Knowledge Systems	Participation enriches design but needs skilled facilitation, capacity building, mutual respect, and flexible methods.
Diversity of Stakeholders	Reflects the complex socio-ecological systems in which NbS are embedded and recognizes the need for cross-sectoral and cross-level coordination.
Mature Stakeholder Approach	Combines formal channels, community processes, and feedback loops for robust involvement.

Table 4

A summary of the structure of the three workshops developed to support the co-design process. Session number, period, description of sessions, and relation with the IUCN standard.

Sessions	Period	Output description	IUCN GS Relation
1st	Before NbS implementation (May - November 2023)	- Spatial validation of the NbS	Criterion 1 Criterion 3
		- Knowledge integration of water management infrastructures	Criterion 5
		- Validation of potential NbS	
2nd	Before NbS implementation (February - April 2024)	- Quantification of stakeholders perception	Criterion 2
		- Integration of stakeholders needs	Criterion 5
		- Strategic assessment (strengths and weaknesses challenges and opportunities)	Criterion 6
3rd	After NbS implementation (February 2025 - ongoing)	- Bridging traditional knowledge with legislation	
		- Comparative assessment against grey infrastructures	Criterion 2 Criterion 3
		- Local stakeholders' validation on the implementation	Criterion 4 Criterion 5
		- Potential for scalability	Criterion 7 Criterion 8

local needs and aspirations, refining the design and inviting stakeholders to engage in more interactive and practical discussions, aligning with Indicator 5.3. It was also analyzed if the NbS properly recognized and responded to the interactions between the economy, society and ecosystems (Indicator 2.1), if it could be integrated with other water infrastructures, if synergies across sectors were possible (Indicator 2.2) and if risk management both within and beyond the specific intervention site (Indicator 2.3) was addressed, aligning with criterion 2. Participants also focused on identifying strengths, weaknesses, and obstacles for FWC-NbS implementation, as well as possible trade-offs (Indicator 6.1), aligning with criterion 6. During the third co-design session, previous criteria were re-evaluated (Criteria 2, 3, 4 and 5) but findings focused on evaluating NbS performance (indicator 7.2), opposing current NbS against "grey" infrastructures or other traditional engineering approaches (indicator 4.3), aligning with criterion 4, and reflected on the solution's potential to be replicated and scaled-up (indicator 8.2) and influence policy (indicator 8.1).

4. Discussion

To ensure the success of NbS - which is about efficiency, cost-effectiveness and resilience - it is essential to implement clear, widely accepted standards that guarantee NbS adequately address the identified societal challenges, are economically, environmentally and socially sustainable, and deliver multiple benefits [54]. Although the IUCN Global Standard was only introduced in 2020, its scientific relevance is already well-supported. Numerous studies highlight the framework's importance in driving positive outcomes for NbS through rigorous design and systematic assessment [38,55,34,56,57]. These studies highlight how the IUCN GS criteria lead to better project design, implementation, and assessment. Applying the Standard has become a baseline practice to define the conceptual boundaries of NbS, preventing the misuse of the term while accounting for diverse environmental and social factors [43]. In this study, the application of the IUCN GS confirmed that all five case studies qualify as authentic NbS, each achieving an overall adherence score exceeding 25%. Presently, as environmental changes increasingly threaten our food, water, income, and health, the role of NbS becomes fundamental in strengthening the link between nature and societal needs [58]. In this work, it was observed that for the five CS, all improved the score in Criterion 1 (Societal Challenges, Supplementary Table 1) after the second assessment or qualified at least as Adequate. It was also noted that all CS succeeded in the identification of societal challenges, particularly those related to water security. Other authors have also supported the necessity of applying the IUCN GS as an overarching assessment framework, in different contexts, such as NbS for river flood management [38] where they found that the Standard, particularly Criterion 7 (Adaptive Management, Supplementary Table 1) could be used to assess project progress which is in line with present findings. For instance, CS1 (Spain) progressed from an 89% to a 100% adherence score in Criterion 7 between the first and second assessment. In addition, adhering to established standards is essential for ensuring that potential trade-offs are systematically identified and managed to optimize overall project outcomes [43,27]. Data from this research confirms that the adherence to the IUCN GS serves as a vital safeguard for NbS by ensuring that potential trade-offs are properly identified and incorporated into the design, as demonstrated in Criterion 6, where positive changes were observed in one indicator for four of the CS. Particularly, socio-economic trade-offs were found in CS4 and CS2 and technical and environmental trade-offs in CS3 and CS2.

The present study revealed a dual outcome: while the Standard provided a robust and systematic framework for design, implementation, and evaluation for the five CS, it also exposed underlying challenges and lessons learnt related to data collection, human resources, funding, and governance. Some of the challenges were already identified during the first assessment, as for Criterion 3 about biodiversity net gain (see supplementary materials), where lack of baseline data and clear metrics to evaluate biodiversity were detected in CS2, CS4 and CS5. This is in line with Seddon et al., [16], who found biodiversity improvement and ecosystem integrity to be an infrequent priority goal in many NbS interventions, especially if not directly targeted. Authors explained that the scarcity in biodiversity-related data is usually related to budget, time and expertise constraints. In the present study, all the CS that identified this challenge, increased their score during the second assessment, such as CS3, that exhibited a substantial improvement, with an enhancement from 42% to 75% in its alignment. These findings support that the application of the Standard contributed to improve NbS design by mitigating potential failures due to poor ecological design and monitoring performance incorporating new data. Nonetheless, it was also observed that the application of the Standard exhibited certain limitations, which became apparent following the second assessment, wherein the score of certain CS underwent a decrease. In CS2, adherence to Criterion 4 (Economic Feasibility) declined from 83% to 58% during the second assessment. This was primarily due to the impossibility of CS2 to

fully operationalize the initially planned cost-benefit analysis within the NATMed project's framework. While non-monetary and longitudinal benefits were identified, they could not be comprehensively integrated as originally intended. The findings outlined above, when considered in conjunction with the results of the internal survey, which identified criterion 4 as one of the most challenging aspects of the IUCN GS Standard, have elucidated the intricacy of this tool application with regard to the provision of an economic perspective for NbS, as also found by Mayor et al., [59]. Also, it supported findings from Cheli et al., [60] who found that the existing body of knowledge regarding NbS in water management present difficulties of assigning monetary value to non-market ecosystem services, such as improved water quality from restored wetlands, which was also found by this study in the natural wetland storage area of CS2.

The present findings partially support those of Berg et al., [38], which suggested that the IUCN GS is a complex tool with technically dense language that may be inaccessible to local practitioners. Results from the internal survey show that the application of the self-assessment was found "hard" and that the guidance from specialized technicians was fundamental for overcoming difficulties. It has been observed that external technical guidance has a positive impact, particularly in instances of initial engagement with the Standard, given its inherent complexity. Nevertheless, this study agrees with Berg et al [38] on the fact that IUCN GS users may encounter difficulties with data collection, particularly when referring to biodiversity socio-economic data. This study also supports Seddon et al. [16] when claiming that small projects often lack the technical capacity to quantify complex biodiversity gains or social "net-benefit" in the specific formats required by the IUCN GS. In regions characterized by vast and complex geographies, the lack of field-based biodiversity data creates spatial sampling biases, distorting species distribution perception, that risk misdirecting scarce financial resources away from high-priority interventions [61,62]. The positive and negative shifts identified through case studies after the second assessment highlight the value of the IUCN GS as a tool for corrective action and continuous improvement. For instance, this was reflected in the positive increase in CS3 for criterion 4 (+75%), due to the actual execution of economic feasibility studies that were not foreseen during the first assessment. Conversely, decreased scores, as in CS5 for indicator 6.2, represent a more realistic understanding of data gaps.

It was also noticed that some CS encountered difficulties for inclusive governance (Criterion 5, Supplementary Table 1) such as in CS5, where existing deficits in the engagement of underrepresented groups were acknowledged. This was also identified by other authors such as Kiss et al. [63] who found that deeper levels of participation are hence limited by inherent institutional structures, the lack of trust among actors involved and that the IUCN GS does not allow users to tailor the assessment to a project context [38]. The present study has also identified that local governance and stakeholders' engagement are frequently disregarded. To palliate this issue, a significant contribution has been made to bridging the gap between standardized global quality assurance (IUCN GS), and localized, bottom-up implementation by applying a multi-method approach, which provides solutions that are more proportionate to the local governance challenges. This is primarily attributable to the incorporation of local knowledge and stakeholder feedback into the decision-making processes via co-design and MedCoP tools. Within the framework of this research, the implementation of three iterative co-design sessions facilitated a nuanced and context-specific evaluation of Criterion 5 (Inclusive Governance). These sessions acted as an operational vehicle to translate the abstract requirement of "inclusivity" into measurable, verifiable metrics. This was observed for instance, during the second co-design session where participants developed exercises to integrate stakeholders' needs and bridge the gap between local knowledge, traditional infrastructures and legislation for all CS. In addition, MedCoP revealed that thanks to the diversity of stakeholders, the need for better cross-sectoral and cross-level coordination was recognized. MedCoP showed some

opportunities for building trust and helped foster public acceptance and ownership of the solutions, supporting the results of Sidle et al. [64] in their study of NbS implementation in a mountainous area in Central Asia. In Martín-Dato et al., [65] authors also found that treatment wetlands in Colombia should be adapted to the local context, and that when criteria can be contextualized in each case, they are better aligned with the Standard purposes.

In the context of the five Mediterranean CS, the early identification of actors through stakeholder mapping and the MedCoP co-design sessions allowed for a comprehensive evaluation of how local participants contribute to project success. By recognizing stakeholders as active partners rather than study subjects, the CS proposed in this work, ensured a meaningful stakeholder engagement, which is fundamentally integral to the IUCN GS, as also found by Ibrahim et al., (2025) [66]. This approach established a tailored participatory baseline, enabling targeted inclusion and a structured engagement model that improved strategic planning and built trust through three levels of involvement. The Stakeholder Mapping and the MedCoP served as a systematic approach that successfully translated complex agricultural friction points, such as water scarcity and power asymmetries, into actionable governance solutions, which contributes to fulfill indicators under Criteria 2, 5, 6, 7 and 8 of the GS. Also, findings herein are valuable for water related agricultural context since lessons learnt, key challenges extracted from the Table 1, can potentially guide future interventions for NbS related to sustainable water management.

Furthermore, the scientific relevance of these findings lies in their ability to resolve the "top-down" limitations often associated with the IUCN GS for smaller projects, as to advance the field of NbS by validating and operationalizing the IUCN GS through a novel, multi-method approach. By using the MedCoP as a vehicle for mutual learning and co-creation, the study successfully integrated stakeholder feedback directly into the design process. This integration not only identified critical barriers to implementation—such as data scarcity, lack of stakeholders' engagement, capacity building, difficulties in valuing intangible benefits— but also enhanced adaptive management by providing a structured feedback loop for real-world implementation challenges. As the MedCoP is intended to persist beyond the NATMed project's completion, it offers a scalable model for the permanent maintenance of NbS within agricultural contexts, ensuring these interventions remain technically sound and socially appropriate.

5. Conclusions

This research addresses the persistent gap between the theoretical design and practical implementation of NbS by validating a multi-methodological framework across five Mediterranean case studies. The results demonstrate that the IUCN GS provides a robust diagnostic for enhancing NbS design, particularly in identifying societal challenges related to water security in rural agricultural contexts. The iterative, two-phase assessment process facilitated a clear roadmap for project enhancement, as evidenced by significant performance gains in adaptive management and economic feasibility across several sites.

However, the application of the Standard also exposed critical operational barriers. The study highlights a persistent data scarcity regarding biodiversity net-gain and socio-economic outcomes, alongside the inherent difficulty of assigning monetary value to non-market ecosystem services like water quality improvement. These findings confirm that small-scale projects often lack the technical capacity or "fee-for-service" models required to meet the Standard's rigorous quantitative expectations without external guidance.

To overcome these institutional and technical hurdles, this work successfully bridged global quality assurance (IUCN GS) with localized bottom-up implementation through the Mediterranean Community of Practice (MedCoP) and iterative co-design. Stakeholder mapping served as the foundational basis for the creation and development of the MedCoP, ensuring its composition was derived from a rigorous analysis

of actor typologies, roles and stakeholders' opinions. This approach guaranteed that the Community of Practice was specifically engineered to resolve the challenges identified during the assessment and stakeholders' analysis. Simultaneously, the MedCoP acted as a data-generation instrument for the IUCN GS evaluations, gathering qualitative and quantitative social dimension data compliant with IUCN requirements. By treating stakeholders as active partners, the project successfully translated complex agricultural friction points—such as water scarcity and power asymmetries—into actionable governance solutions. Ultimately, this research provides a foundational "stress test" for the methodology, establishing that prioritizing biodiversity and socio-economic baseline data during the initial design phase is a critical determinant for the successful replication and long-term sustainability of NbS. By applying the same framework to different socio-economic contexts and climatic zones, practitioners can move beyond theoretical modeling to validate the robustness and general applicability of the multi-method approach.

This manuscript makes a vital contribution to the emerging body of literature on the IUCN GS and advances the field of NbS by validating and operationalizing the IUCN GS through a novel, multi-method approach. It reinforces findings that deeper participation is often limited by institutional structures, using the Mediterranean Community of Practice (MedCoP) to foster transdisciplinary collaboration. To enhance the robustness of future NbS interventions, this work highlights a clear roadmap: prioritizing the collection of biodiversity and socio-economic baseline data during the initial design phase—rather than as an afterthought—is a critical determinant for the overall success and validation of Nature-based Solutions.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the author(s) used Gemini and Microsoft Copilot in order to improve the readability and language of the manuscript. After using this tool/service, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and take(s) full responsibility for the content of the published article.

Data availability

Datasets of the two assessments against the IUCN GS are available at the Zenodo platform (First assessment: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17256089> Second assessment: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17415330>). Dataset of the internal survey on the use of the IUCN GS within NATMed will be shared under request.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Sara Peláez-Sánchez: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Claudia Sánchez:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Raquel Marijuan:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Project administration. **Barbara Díez:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Olympia Papadopoulou:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation. **Patricia Marín Poveda:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation. **Andrés Florencio Alcántara Valero:** Validation. **Jesús Iglesias Saugar:** Validation, Supervision. **Raúl Sánchez:** Visualization, Validation. **Isabel Martín:** Writing – review & editing, Validation. **Ampas Vasileios:** Writing – review & editing, Validation. **Theodoros Stavrakas:** Writing – review & editing, Validation. **Alberto Carletti:** Writing – review & editing, Validation. **Alessandra Paulotto:** Writing – review & editing, Validation. **Başar Şirin:** Writing – review & editing, Validation. **M. Tolga Esetlili:** Writing – review & editing, Validation. **Irem Orman:**

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper

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Supplementary materials

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